

Role of Job Scheduling and Sequencing on Service Performance of Small-scale Fashion Design Outfits in Osogbo, Osun State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study investigated the role of job scheduling and sequencing on the service performance of small-scale fashion outfits in Osogbo, Osun State. The population of the study was 2273 SMEs in Osun State registered with SMEDAN. The sample size was 16 small-scale fashion design outfits were purposively selected from the study population. Ten staff were randomly selected from each fashion design outfit in the Osogbo metropolis, totaling 160 respondents. A structured questionnaire was adapted to gather relevant information from the respondents. Data collected were analysed with tables, mean averages, and regression model. Findings showed that fashion design outfits use scheduling and sequencing with a 3.0 mean. Also, customers were satisfied with the service level, with a mean score of 3.0. The awareness and usage level of job scheduling and sequencing among small-scale fashion design outfits was high. The study concluded that job scheduling and sequencing affect the performance of small-scale fashion design outfits. Fashion design outfits should kindly adopt job scheduling and sequencing for better organisational performance that would bring about; customer satisfaction, customer retention, facility utilisation, and high profitability.

Keywords: Scheduling, Sequencing, Performance, Intention, Fashion designer outfit, Small-scale

Introduction

Scheduling and sequencing are like twin brothers in operation management (Johnson, 2014). Scheduling deals with the time planned for a job while sequencing from the order through which the task would be practiced. The technique has been a key strategy in ensuring the appropriateness of job execution in an organisation. The target of applying the technique is to optimize facility utilisation by minimising machine idle time and late completion of Jobs (Stephenson, 2014). Customers will always appreciate and value such service.

The timing and use of resources within an organisation are determined by scheduling and sequencing. Scheduling pertains to utilising tools and facilities, planning human activities, and receiving materials under the operations function (manufacturing and services) (Amogu, 2005). Operations scheduling is viewed as a short-term issue. In contrast, facility location, plant and equipment acquisition, and aggregate planning are considered long-term and intermediate-term, respectively. As a result, prior to the production of the actual output (such as finished goods), scheduling is typically the last step in the transformation process in the decision-making hierarchy. Due to the limitations imposed by these longer-term decisions, scheduling decisions are made (Olu, 2017). Scheduling objectives typically involve making compromises between competing demands for the effective use of labour and equipment, lead times, inventory levels, and processing times.

Effective scheduling and sequencing have become more crucial recently, according to Nosek and Wilson (2001). This rise is partly attributable to the acceptance of just-in-time and lean manufacturing. Stock-outs are now much more likely due to the resulting drop in inventory levels and subsequent increase in replenishment frequency. The Internet has also increased the pressure to plan effectively. Small-scale enterprises are gradually growing in the Nigerian economy due to their grassroots approach and start-up capital (National Bureau of Statistics, 2017). Small Enterprises Development Corporation (SEDCO, 2010) is defined as an organisation that publishes general-purpose financial statements for external users but does not have public accountability. A company

is considered small-scale if it has a total capital of over N1.5 million but under N50 million, including working capital but excluding the cost of land, and employs between 11 and 100 people (SMEDAN, 2018). They formed an impetus for economic growth in Nigeria, and it is a business that employed a large workforce with a high volume of sales in the Nigerian economy (Fabayo, 2009). The nature of small-scale organisations is unique because they exist in all sectors of the economy. They are an organisation with few workers, small capital, and equipment. They operate at the grassroots of the economy and adopt a niche approach to penetrating the market (SMEDAN, 2017).

Organisations that engage in producing human wear and fashion accessories (Oke, 2004). They deal with micro-production activities and trade their final products in the market. Performance index measurements for such organisations include; profitability, customer retention, product quality, labor-turn-over among others. An organisation that needs to catch up to the above is performing poorly (Oni, 2016). The target of all organisations is to perform very well. A look into job scheduling and sequencing in their job execution will be worthwhile, hence this study.

Statement of the problem

Scheduling and sequencing are the basis of organisational performance and growth. This growth was also affected by the nitpick of the customers at the time lag in delivering their service, thus serving as part of the problems catalysing the breakdown of any organisation, be it small or large. In the developed world, scheduling and sequencing formed the bedrock of an organisation's formal practices, which is yet to be ascertained in Nigeria. Vohra (2017), in his empirical study titled "Application of Operations Research Technique in Effective Management," unraveled the fact that the scheduling and sequencing technique is the least embraced method in many African counties. This brings about issues of ignoring the methods despite the benefits, as Nosek and Wilson (2001) highlighted. Fashion design outlets are a core sector where customer waiting is peculiar. Satisfying the customers is the apex aim of management. Application of scheduling and sequencing can help in realising this aim. This study was therefore designed to examine the problem of scheduling and sequencing among fashion design outlets in Osogbo, Osun State, Nigeria. The study would be of immense importance to fashion outlets in Osun State and other parts of the country. It would allow the management to assess the relevance of scheduling and sequencing in their workplace.

Objectives of the study

The study's main objective was to investigate the role of job scheduling and sequencing on the service performance of SMEs fashion design outlets in Osogbo, Osun State, Nigeria. The specific objectives were to:

- i. investigate job scheduling and sequencing usage by small-scale fashion outfits in Osogbo, Osun State.
- ii. determine the effect of job scheduling and sequencing on the performance of small-scale fashion outfits in Osogbo, Osun State.

Research questions

- i. To what extent do job scheduling and sequencing usage influence the service performance of small-scale fashion outfits in Osogbo, Osun State?
- ii. How do job scheduling and sequencing enhance the service performance of small-scale fashion outfits in Osogbo, Osun State?

Conceptual review

Sequencing is concerned with the order in which jobs are processed. It is necessary to determine the order in which tasks are completed at work centres and individual workstations. The situation may become complicated when work centres are overloaded and time-consuming jobs are involved.

Regarding the cost of waiting to be processed and idle time at work centres, the order of processing can be extremely important (Singh, 2012). The sequencing and scheduling of services in the service sectors differ greatly from those in manufacturing. This is because services are intangible, they cannot be stocked or stored, and service requests are frequently irrational. As seen in dining establishments, movie theatres, and theme parks, unpredictable demand makes labour scheduling challenging. Customers dislike waiting, so labour needs to be scheduled to reduce the customer wait. Estimated arrival times and service rates are used in queueing theory to determine the ideal staffing ratio. Flexibility can be incorporated into the service operation through temporary workers, available on-call employees, and cross-training.

One of the most crucial aspects of a university's work is the ability to schedule students, faculty, classrooms, labs, audiovisual equipment, and computers. According to an expert, service scheduling becomes more challenging when more than one resource must be coordinated and scheduled. Cancellations are frequent and can further disrupt and confuse the scheduling process, making matters more difficult (Nosek & Wilson, 2001). Jonah (2017) emphasised the scheduling and sequencing presumptions, which might only be true occasionally.

Scheduling in high-volume systems

Standardised tools and processes that perform identical or strikingly similar operations on clients or goods define high-volume systems. A high level of labour and asset utilisation is desired. Numerous loading and sequence decisions are made during the design process because of the highly repetitive nature of these systems. Line balancing and flow system design are two important components of system design. Allocating the necessary tasks to workstations in a way that satisfies technical (sequencing) requirements and maintains a balance in terms of equal work times across stations is known as line balancing. It yields the highest output rate while also maximising the use of personnel and equipment. The specialisation of job tasks in these systems could lead to worker dissatisfaction, and flow system design considers this. High work rates are frequently achieved by breaking the work into a series of relatively simple tasks assigned to different workers (Ile, 2002).

Gantt chart

Henry Gantt, an early 1900s management pioneer, is honoured by having his name attached to Gantt charts. He suggested using a visual aid for scheduling and loading. They aid users in comprehending how resources are being used or are intended to be used within a given time frame. The Gantt chart can be used by managers to create trial-and-error schedules and gauge the effects of various arrangements (Singh, 2012). The load chart and schedule chart are the two most popular Gantt chart types and are most pertinent to our discussion. The loading and idle times for machines or departments are displayed on a load chart, which indicates when specific tasks are scheduled to begin and end and where idle time can be anticipated (Johnson, 2017). A glance at a schedule chart reveals which jobs are on schedule and on time. This can help the scheduler redo loading assignments for better utilisation of the work centres. On this Gantt chart type, the vertical axis shows the orders or jobs in progress, while the horizontal axis represents time. The most frequently used scheduling tools are Gantt charts. They do, however, have some restrictions. It must be updated frequently to keep the chart up to date. The chart also ignores the costs of alternative loadings and the possibility of varying processing times between work centres (Nwandu, 2006).

Empirical review

Yusuf et al. (2015) investigated the queueing theory and customer satisfaction with a population of 300 customers from the first bank in Nigeria. Taro Yamane sample technique was used to select 250 respondents. The instrument used was a questionnaire. The return rate of the questionnaire was 200, which represents 80% of the sample size used for the analysis of the study. The statistical method used was SPSS, using regression analysis and a model. The study discovered that most

bank customers are dissatisfied with the wait times they encounter before receiving service. Based on this discovery, the study advised an effective and efficient application of queuing theory, which can be especially useful in banks with high out-customer workloads and those that offer multiple points of service. Service managers can make decisions that improve the satisfaction of all relevant groups, including customers, staff, and management, by better understanding queuing theory. This implies that the study can be carried out in another field of study as a knowledge gap.

Nosek and Wilson (2001) examined the queuing theory in relation to operations management. The approach was previously applied to evaluate staff schedules, work environments, productivity, customer wait times, and environments related to customer wait times. Therefore, queuing theory can be used in pharmacies to evaluate various variables, including staffing levels, patient wait times, prescription fill times, and counseling times. The study revealed that queuing theory applications might be especially helpful with heavy outpatient workloads and those that offer multiple points of service. Service managers can make choices that improve the satisfaction of all relevant groups, including customers, staff, and management, by better understanding queuing theory. The study revealed an empirical gap.

According to Bonga (2021), a company's ability to grow and survive depends heavily on adhering to its core business principles. Customers find it inconvenient to wait in a queue, and businesses incur costs. Queuing theory is a mathematical approach to studying standing in lines. The study's findings are presented, which assesses how well a queuing model identifies the efficiency parameters for restaurant queuing systems. It analyses data gathered over three weeks from Beitbridge's Croc Foods Restaurant using Little's Theorem. According to the study, 84 customers are served per hour, and 60 customers arrive on average per hour. The system utilisation factor was 71.43%, the probability of having no customers wait was 0.2857, there were, on average, 1.782 customers waiting, and the average waiting time was 0.0298 hours. The model was found to be inferior for the Croc Foods restaurant when the single-server and multi-server models were compared in the study. A survey of 171 participants yielded the following results: approximately 43.3% of customers are dissatisfied with the nature of waiting lines. About 69% of customers have at least been turned away on regular occasions because of the lines. Therefore, existing customers are valuable in the long run, and the study has emphasised the importance of constantly monitoring their changing needs and improving the amount of time spent serving them.

Methodology

A descriptive survey research design was used for the study. The study population was 2273 SMEs in Osun State registered with SMEDAN. The sample size was 16 small-scale fashion design outfits purposively selected from the study population. Ten staff was randomly selected from each fashion design outfit, totaling 160 respondents. Data was sourced with the aid of a questionnaire. The questionnaire was administered to respondents, and the Data gathered were analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics.

Results and discussion

Table 3.1: Accept any term with a mean mark of 2.50 or above and reject if otherwise.

Degree of Involvement	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Do you deliver at the appropriate time?	160	3.0	1.87
There is a time lag in your service delivery.	160	2.0	1.11
Customers are satisfied with your service.	160	3.0	1.29
Do you agree with the term first come first?	160	4.0	1.15
Is the term applied in your outlet?	160	3.0	1.21
Has it helped to increase your workability?	160	3.5	1.09
Do scheduling and sequencing please your customer?	160	2.5	1.38
Do you give room for feedback?	160	3.0	1.07

Source: Researchers' Field Survey 2022

Decision Rule: Accept any term with a mean mark of 2.50 or above and reject if otherwise

Table 3.1 presents the analysis of the data obtained on small-scale fashion outfits' usage of job scheduling and sequencing in their operations. Item one has a mean mark of 3.0 and a standard deviation of 1.87, which means that the outfits deliver their services at the appropriate time. Item two has a mean mark of 2.0 and a standard deviation of 1.11, below the cut-off mark of 2.5, suggesting no time lag within the chosen fashion outfits. Item three has a mean mark of 3.0 and a standard deviation of 1.29, meaning that customers are satisfied with the service delivered by the fashion outfits. From the analysis made on item four, an aggregate means a mark of 4.0 and a standard deviation of 1.15 agreed with the first come, first serve. Item five has a mean mark of 3.0 and a standard deviation of 1.21, meaning that the first come and first serve technique is applied in their fashion outfits. On item number six, a mean mark of 3.5 and standard deviation of 1.09 agreed that the use of sequencing and scheduling helped improve their workability. Item seven has a mean score of 2.5 and a standard deviation of 1.38, which means that the sequencing and scheduling method pleases the customers. The last item on the list has a mean mark of 3.0 and a standard deviation of 1.07, which says that the outlets allow for feedback.

Table 3.2: Usage level of the scheduling and sequencing rules by the small-scale fashion outfits

S/N	Scheduling and Sequencing Rules	CR	N	S	ST.	O	A	T	WM	RATIN G
1	Earlier Due Date (EDD.)	13	2	18	23	73	31	160	3.5	Often
2	First in the System First Serve	0	7	3	18	43	89	160	4.3	Often
3	Long Processing Time (LPT)	13	19	6	66	32	24	160	2.9	ST
4	Short Processing Time (SPT.)	1	4	31	40	63	21	160	3	S.T.
5	Moore Procedures	23	34	14	26	30	33	160	2.7	ST
6	Gantt Chart	28	73	11	25	12	11	160	1.7	Never
7	Computer Programming	0	1	12	74	32	41	160	3.6	Often
	Grand Totals	78	140	95	272	285	250	1120	3.16	ST

Source: Field Survey, 2022

Key: CR= Cannot rate, N= Never, S= Seldomly, ST=Sometime, O= Often, A=Always, T=Total, WM=Weighted Mean. Codes: Never is coded 1, Seldom=2, Sometime=3, Often=4, Always=5

Analysis confirms that most small-scale fashion design outfits often use the earliest due date rule; in the system first serve rule and computer programming method with a weighted mean score of 3.5, 4.3, and 3.6, respectively. Long process time, short processing time, and Moore procedure rules are sometimes used by small-scale scale fashion design outfits. The mean score of 2.9, 3, and 2.7, respectively, affirms it. The small-scale fashion design outfits never use the Gantt chart method, with a mean score of 1.7. The comprehensive analysis shows that most small-scale fashion design outfits sometimes used job scheduling & sequencing rules in their operation, with a mean score of 3.16. This affirms that small-scale fashion design outfits are aware of and use the job scheduling & sequencing rules in their operations.

Regression analysis

Table 3: Model summary

R	R square	Adjusted R square	Std. Error of Estimate	F-Statistic
.726	.527	.439	.2296886	49.4

Source: Research Analysis, 2022

Table 4: Job scheduling and sequencing, and performance

Model	Un- standardizes coefficient	Std Error	Standardized coefficient	t -Statistic
	B		Beta	
Constant	1.887	.128		1.236
x_1	1.02	.026	-.349	- 1.049
x_2	0.039	.012	-.585	0.266
x_3	0.24	.5	-.017	- .061
x_4	1.008	.006	.568	1.349

				0.457
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Regression line; $Y = \alpha_1 + x_1 + x_2 + x_3 + x_4 + e$

The effect of job scheduling and sequencing were investigated from the result of respondents where,

Y = Job Scheduling & sequencing

X₁ = Customer's Satisfaction

X₂ = Administration effectiveness

X₃ = Profitability

X₄ = Facility utilisation.

$$Y = 1.887 + 1.02X_1 + 0.039X_2 + 0.24X_3 + 1.008X_4$$

The coefficient of intercept c has a value of (1.887) and is significant with a p-value of 1.36 at the 95% significant level. The scheduling and sequencing rules coefficient has a positive value of 1.02 at a 5% significant level with a p-value of 1.049. Also, the coefficient of all the dependent variables is positive, which shows an increase and better performance by the small-scale fashion design outfits. The most critical factor which affects job scheduling and sequencing performance is the increase in service quality and customer satisfaction.

The regression analysis below shows the relationship between job scheduling and sequencing and the performance of small-scale fashion outfits. The coefficient of multiple determinations (R_z) explained uniquely by the independent variables is 52.7%. This indicates a change in the performance of small-scale fashion outfits due to job scheduling and sequencing applications. The 47.3% discrepancies are other factors affecting performance and not the model. The Constant factor is 1.887, which shows the dependent (y) value when all independent variables are 0.

Conclusion

Based on the findings from this study, the following conclusions were made; Small-scale fashion design outfits in Osogbo, Osun State, are familiar with job scheduling and sequencing techniques in operations. They also use these techniques always in their operations. Scheduling and sequencing technique is helpful to small-scale fashion design outfits in Osogbo, Osun State, in customer satisfaction, administration effectiveness, profitability, and facility utilisation. It brings about increasing the better performance of work rate and customer satisfaction.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made based on the study's findings; all small-scale fashion design outfits must embrace job scheduling and sequencing for better organisational performance. Training on job scheduling and sequencing should be organised periodically for staff of small-scale fashion design outfits to improve their usage level on the technique for better performance.

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